

JUST A MOMENT, PLEASE!

IMPROVING THE OVERALL USER EXPERIENCE, MOMENT BY MOMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this workshop a practical model (Moment-Message-Design) is presented to give designers who focus on the interactions with products the opportunity to explore the impact of the message on the 'conversation' (interaction) with the user. A focus on the combination of specific single moments, conversations and the (perceived) messages will enable designers to improve the overall user experience moment by moment.

KEYWORDS: *Conversational Design, Emotion, Interaction Design, Message, Moment*

INTRODUCTION

A couple of months ago, one of the authors went out to buy a gift for his wife. After browsing a couple of stores on the street, he ended up at a store where beauty and wellness products are sold. He found a nice set of perfumes and decided to purchase them. The lady behind the counter asked if it was a gift, and they had a short chat about the products and whom they were meant for, all while she was gift-wrapping them. After paying, she suddenly surprised him by getting from behind the counter, stepping up in front of him and presenting the gift in a nice looking bag in the way you would only present and hand-over something very valuable to someone. While doing so, she told him to enjoy giving this nice gift to his wife and looked him in the eye. These actions, combined with this personalized message, completely changed the overall purchase experience, from a cold transaction to a personal and even meaningful short interaction.

In this example, a real life interaction between customer and service provider was used to illustrate the power of a) a moment (paying), b) a conversation (about the payment, the gift and the purpose/meaning), and c) a personalized message

(attention to the client and understanding of the underlying goals) to achieve a specific emotional impact.

Even though the abovementioned example was about human-to-human interaction, similarities can be found in human-product interactions. For example, a focus on single moments in relation to product-use, referred to as 'micro-interactions' (Saffer, 2013). Examples of micro-interactions are: switching a product on or off, connecting one device to another, or changing a setting. In the abovementioned example, micro-interactions could be the act of paying, handing over the gift or the question of who the gift is for. Additionally, the concept of conversation is not new in the discipline of Interaction Design (e.g. Nickerson, 1976). Conversational design, as it has been referred to (Leong, 2004), is focused on designing human-product interactions that proceed as smoothly and efficiently as real-life conversations between people. Conversational design assumes that both the user and the product are *cooperating* in the conversation, also known as the cooperative principle of conversations. This assumption implies that both 'parties' can expect certain behavior from one another. For example, the product (and thus the designer) can expect the prospect user to have a certain level of knowledge before using it and engaging in the 'conversation'. A simple example is that a car

designer can assume the prospect driver has passed his or her driver's exam and therefore expect specific skills and behavior. Although both a focus on the specific actions in a single moment of product use (micro-interactions) and a conversational approach can be of great help in designing successful interactive products or services, they give little attention to the resulting emotional impact of the interaction and thus to that (important) part of the overall user experience. In this paper, it is argued that the intended message and especially the perceived message are key influences on the emotional impact of moments in human-product interactions, and should therefore be considered and explored by designers.

A practical model is presented to give designers who focus on the interactions with products the opportunity to explore the impact of the message in the 'conversation' (interaction) with the user. A focus on the combination of specific moments, conversations and the (perceived) messages will enable designers to improve the overall user experience moment by moment.

MOMENT-MESSAGE-DESIGN

To achieve the goal of gaining insight into the intended message of the design and its impact, a model that prescribes a specific design method has been developed: the Moment-Message-Design model. The model consists of three steps: 1) describing the *moment*, 2) conceiving a *message* and 3) creating *design solutions*.

The model intends to break conventional ways of following a (interaction) design process and create an opportunity to introduce new considerations, such as 'what's the message I want to communicate with my design?'. So, instead of regular product design thinking, "what more features can we add?", the question becomes "how can we tell our story better?". The model can help designers answering this question.

Figure 1: The Moment-Message-Design-model.

Step 1: The moment

In this step the designer describes the moment he is designing for as accurately as possible. For example, a customer of a telecommunications operator expects to receive a certain

mobile phone and finds a different phone is delivered. Now, a designer wants to create a solution so that both parties have a desirable situation as quickly as possible. The designer is to describe in detail all the key players of this moment and what their role is. This gives an overview of opportunities to intervene with a design, and makes way for the next step: Conceive a message.

Step 2: The Message

This is the most important step in the model. First, the designer consults his or her own feelings and emotions to formulate an intended message (e.g., by roleplaying). This should be kept as abstract as possible, for example, think about how instrumental music can deliver a message without the lyrics, or like the non-communicated intentions you feel during a conversation. This step is more about the intentions and empathizing with the situation than about the techniques to deliver the message. These techniques are left open as much as possible and are created in the next step: Create design solutions.

Step 3: Design Solutions

The message can be delivered in many different ways. This is the time where designers brainstorm about ways to translate it. For example, saying 'we're sorry we sent you the wrong product' can be written in an e-mail, told via a phone call or communicated in a humorous video about people making mistakes. But many more original and impactful ways are probably still undiscovered. By knowing your situation (moment) and the message you want to communicate, you get a large number of new opportunities for design solutions. As a brand or company, this could give you the advantage you need over competitors or, better still, show what's different and unique about you by more effectively communicating your vision.

WORKSHOP GOALS

This half-day workshop will provide (interaction) designers the opportunity to experiment with an approach that enables them to explore the impact of their design (message) in specific moments. The Moment-Message-Design model provides them with a practical framework to improve the user experience of their designs, but at the same time does not presume to have all the answers. The workshop is meant for designers of all disciplines; however, it is expected that the approach will mostly resonate with interaction designers, or designers with a specific focus on the interaction between product and user.

OUTLINE AND ACTIVITIES

1. Introduction to conversational approaches, challenges and opportunities.
2. The Moment-Message-Design model: Bit-sized theory and a description of the model. Short exercises to understand the model and experience the approach.

3. Case introduction: What's today's challenge? Groups of 3, exercise to apply the model.
4. Presentations: Show each other your results and what you've learned.
5. Closing statements.

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